

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOFT SKILLS IN EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL INTEGRATION

Shodmonova Khadicha Alisher qizi

English teacher at the First Academic Lyceum of the Tashkent State
University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13751633>

Abstract. This article explores soft skills, including communication skills, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence, which are crucial for personal advancement, employability, and social cohesion.

Key words: Soft skills. World Economic Forum, Education, Technological Integration, problem-solving, Resilience

INTRODUCTION

In the world of technological modernization, the significance of soft skills has changed our perspectives for the better. The development of automation and artificial intelligence has manipulated people into believing that technical skills are the most important. However, that is not true in most of the cases. Soft skills which include communication, critical thinking as well as teamwork, has played a vital role more than ever before. These skills will be essential to guide and prepare young people to pave many challenges in today's innovative world. As per the latest reports by the World Economic Forum, during the next five years, social soft skills and emotional intelligence will become even more crucial than technical skills. Employers want to hire people who has the ability to think creatively, solve problems in the modern way and blend in well with others. For decades employers as well as educators frequently complain about a lack in soft skills among graduates from tertiary education institutions. Predominantly missed are communication skills, but additional knowledge in business or project management is also ranking highly on the list of missing skills desirable for graduates entering the business world. Skill-biased technology change and advances in AI have polarized the demand for skills by substituting routine tasks and complementing abstract and complex ones. (Keng, 2024)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Before going any further in debating the importance of soft skills we have to clarify the question "What exactly are soft skills?" This basic question is not easy to answer, because the perception of what is a soft skill differs from context to context. A subject may be considered a soft skill in one particular area, and may be considered a hard skill in another(Keng, 2024) On top of it the understanding of what should be recognised as a soft skill varies widely. Knowledge in project

management for instance is “nice to have” for an electrical engineer, but it is a “must to have” for a civil engineer. Training in cultural awareness might be useful for a chemist, but it is an absolute necessity for public or human resources management in societies of diverse cultures. These skills are important for success in multiple industries, including information technology. Despite the fact that soft skills are becoming more essential than ever, majority of the students are not taught them in traditional classroom world. But, the rise of educational technology, or EdTech, is helping students fill the stereotypical gap. EdTech tools are designed in such a way that can help students get integral life skills that are not usually taught in an academic environment. These talents meet individual and social requirements, according to Cinque (2016) and the Indicators Project. Educational academics and organizations advocate integrating non cognitive talents into curricular solutions. In addition to personal progress, these skills promote social cohesiveness and economic growth,

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soft skills can compel a variety of jobs in the fields of communication, education, finance banking, etc. However, keep in mind that demands keep changing in every industry. Keep track of these requirements. In this article, you will go through understanding the reasons behind the significance of soft skills in contemporary education. Here are the 9 significance of soft skills in contemporary education and professional pathways(Riva, 2017)

1. Adaptability

One of the defining features of the modern world is its rapid pace of change. New technologies, industries, and global challenges emerge constantly, depending individuals to adapt quickly and effectively. The significance of soft skills like adaptability and flexibility is invaluable in this context.

In education, fostering adaptability means encouraging students to explore different subjects, teaching methodologies, and problem-solving approaches. This allows them to develop the mental agility needed to succeed in an ever-changing job market..

2. Communication

Effective communication is a linchpin of success in almost every field. The significance of soft skills related to communication, consisting of active listening, empathy, and the ability to convey ideas clearly, are highly sought after by employers.

In education, the advancement of communication skills goes beyond reading and writing. It includes fostering the ability to engage in constructive discussions,

provide and receive feedback, and work collaboratively on projects. These skills not only help students excel academically but also prepare them for a seamless transition into the workforce.

3. Problem-Solving

The ability to analyze complex issues, think critically, and develop innovative solutions is paramount in modern careers. The significance of soft skills related to problem-solving, such as creativity, critical thinking, and analytical reasoning, empowers individuals to tackle challenges and seize opportunities effectively. Educational institutions are increasingly recognizing the importance of problem-solving skills.

4. Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence, often referred to as EQ, is a vital soft skill that encompasses self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and interpersonal relationships. In both education and careers, individuals with high EQ are better equipped to navigate complex social situations, manage stress, and build meaningful connections with others.

5. Time Management and Organization

The demands of modern education and careers can be overwhelming. The significance of soft skills related to time management and organization, including setting priorities, managing deadlines, and staying focused, are essential for success.

Educational institutions can help students develop these skills by teaching effective study habits, providing time management resources, and promoting a healthy work-life balance.

6. Resilience

Resilience is a critical soft skill that empowers individuals to bounce back from setbacks, adapt to adversity, and maintain a positive outlook even in challenging situations. In both education and careers, resilience is indispensable for navigating setbacks, failures, and periods of uncertainty.

7. Networking and Relationship Building

The ability to network and build meaningful relationships is a valuable soft skill that extends beyond the confines of traditional education and into the realm of careers. In the professional world, networking can open doors to opportunities, mentorship, and collaboration.

8. Cultural Competence and Diversity

In our increasingly interconnected global society, cultural competence and the ability to work effectively in diverse settings are essential soft skills. Individuals

who possess cultural sensitivity and an understanding of different perspectives are better equipped to thrive in multicultural workplaces and educational environments.

9. Digital Literacy

In the digital age, digital literacy has become a fundamental soft skill. It encompasses the ability to navigate digital tools and technologies, critically evaluate online information, and leverage digital platforms for communication and productivity.

Educational institutions play a crucial role in equipping students with digital literacy skills by integrating technology into the learning process, teaching online etiquette, and emphasizing the responsible use of digital resources. These skills are vital for academic success and are increasingly demanded in the modern workplace.

Conclusion

As you learned above, soft skills have merged as a powerful differentiator. When technical knowledge is grabbing high pace and the ability to adapt and communicate effectively skills are offering high-salary jobs in the market. The ability to navigate through complicated problems and social dynamics, lead teams and manage time is prioritized by employers as well as educators. Numerous educational institutions are including soft skills in their curriculum to make their students ready to face the modern challenges in an advanced world(Riva, 2017)

To conclude, soft skills must be taught to prepare kids for contemporary life. Skills like these complement academic and technical knowledge to help people succeed in challenging social and professional settings. Although identifying, teaching, and assessing soft skills is difficult, educators must provide comprehensive frameworks and novel techniques. Google Classroom and other platforms help students acquire soft skills for the current job market and succeed in a complicated and changing environment(van Heerden et al., 2023)

Conclusion:

1. Keng, S.-H. (2024). The Effect of Soft Skills on Academic Outcomes. The B.E. Journal of Economic Analysis & Policy, 24(1), 35–67. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bejeap-2022-0342>
2. Riva, M. G. (2017). Clinical-pedagogical reflections on soft skills in formative pathways for the education professions. Pedagogia Oggi, 15(2). <https://ojs.pensamultimedia.it/index.php/siped/article/view/2400>

3. van Heerden, A., Jelodar, M. B., Chawynski, G., & Ellison, S. (2023). A study of the soft skills possessed and required in the construction sector. *Buildings*, 13(2), 522.